

СУФИАН ЭЛУАКИЛИ

*студент, каф. фізики, механіческий ф-т, ХНАДУ.
Научный руководитель – Волосюк М.А., к.ф.-м.н., доц., каф. фізики,
механіческий ф-т, ХНАДУ.*

**COMPARISON OF EDUCATION SYSTEMS OF MOROCCO
AND UKRAINE**

This paper is devoted to the results of comparing the education systems of Morocco and Ukraine.

Morocco currently has a law on compulsory 9-year education, but not all children graduate from school, since after the 5th grade, most children have to leave their native villages to boarding schools and not everyone decides. Moroccan education copied from France: primary classes - 5 years; medium - 4 years; older children – 3 years. At the end of the 12th grade, students who have passed the exams are given a certificate, but only 47% of students receive it, which prevents others from entering higher education institutions.

In the opinion of the teachers themselves, in Morocco exaggerated requirements for passing exams. For example, to enter a medical university, you need to score 16 points out of 20, and few people succeed. Because for all of Morocco today, only 17 thousand doctors. A few years ago, a Moroccan boy scored 19 out of 20 points in his exams. This case was reported on central television, he was issued a royal prize and was given the choice to go to any higher educational institution.

However, entering a university does not mean finishing it. Morocco has very high requirements for passing tests and exams. After receiving a Moroccan diploma, highly qualified specialists are invited to work in France and Spain, from where, by the way, they very rarely return, which is also one of the problems of Moroccan education.

The problems of education should also include the fact that education in schools and universities in Morocco is not conducted in Arabic, mainly children study in French schools, as this is considered the most prestigious. Ifrane is one of the most prestigious private universities, where studies are conducted in French and English.

Speaking about the education system of Morocco, one cannot but say about the Islamic education system. There are theological faculties in Moroccan universities, where most Moroccans study. Most mosques provide training for women after the service. The Qur'anic schools run by the Ministry of Religion remained in almost all 16 regions of Morocco.

So, Moroccan education is prestigious, but getting it is very difficult. Therefore, many Moroccans leave to study in other countries, for example, to Ukraine, since in most cases it turns out to be easier and cheaper. However, having received a Ukrainian diploma, a Moroccan has to prove his knowledge in Morocco every year.

In Ukraine, general secondary education is compulsory and is obtained in various types of educational institutions, mainly in secondary schools. It has three degrees: I - primary school (1-4 grades), provides primary general education, II - basic school (5-9 grades), provides basic general secondary education; III - high school (grades 10-11), provides a complete general secondary education.

Educational institutions of various levels of accreditation operate in the Ukrainian system of higher education: colleges, institutes, universities, and academies that train highly qualified specialists of various profiles. Foreign students receive not only theoretical knowledge, but also acquire practical skills. Ukraine has become a party to the Bologna Declaration since 2005 and has a standardized educational system along with 46 other European countries, which increases the mobility of students and graduates.

Ukraine is a hospitable and beautiful country with a European education system. More than 63 thousand foreign students who came from 152 countries of the world study at Ukrainian universities today. And every year their number is growing. To enter the universities of Ukraine, foreign citizens do not need to take exams and pass testing. Most universities organize preparatory courses for foreign applicants. The cost of training in Ukraine is significantly lower than in Europe or North America. In Ukraine, different training options are available for foreign citizens: undergraduate, graduate, postgraduate education. You can study remotely and in the correspondence department. The language of instruction to choose from – Ukrainian, English, Russian. In Ukrainian universities you can get a specialty: medical, legal, economic, engineering, technical, humanitarian, etc.

Studying abroad provides an opportunity to explore another country and gain international communication skills. International friendship expands the understanding of other cultures. International experience gained during training is welcomed by employers. Therefore, in our time, studying abroad is very prestigious.

ПОРІВНЯННЯ СИСТЕМ ОСВІТИ МАРОККО ТА УКРАЇНИ

Розглянуто переваги та проблеми отримання освіти студентом в Марокко і в Україні, звернено увагу на позитивні і негативні моменти, що виникають в процесі навчання. Висловлено побажання, які могли б поліпшити якість підготовки іноземних студентів в Україні.

Ключові слова: *система освіти, іноземний студент, міжнародна комунікація.*

COMPARISON OF EDUCATION SYSTEMS OF MOROCCO AND UKRAINE

The advantages and problems of obtaining education by students in Morocco and Ukraine are considered, positive and negative points that arise in the learning process are noted. Wishes were expressed that could improve the quality of training of foreign students in Ukraine.

Key words: *education system, foreign student, international communication.*